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INSURANCE AND INDEMNIFICATION IN GOVERNMENT CONTRACTS FOR SPACE AND DEFENSE

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ABSTRACT

The US federal government is becoming increasingly dependent on commercial partnerships for its space capabilities in the 21st century. With federal awards for space services exceeding \$29.9 billion in 2023 alone, the financial stakes for both agencies and contractors are immense. This paper identifies the different species of risk that commercial space companies face, specifically, losses from misadventure, from foreign interference, and from third-party liability. While commercial insurance and statutory indemnification mechanisms, such as those under the Commercial Space Launch Act and Public Law 85-804, provide a partial solution, they fall short in covering losses caused by foreign adversaries. Due to the prevalence in the private insurance market of exclusion clauses for hostile acts and restrictive definitions in certain procurement contracts, like “unusually hazardous” activities, many space contractors remain critically underprotected. This gap poses not only a prohibitive economic hazard to some companies but also undermines a broader national interest in fostering a resilient, diverse, and competitive base of space contractors.

The paper recommends a legislative solution: a framework that would require contractors to acquire the maximum amount of insurance available from the marketplace while also providing government-backed indemnification for any additional loss caused by foreign interference. Such a system would both mitigate risk for contractors and reinforce critical U.S. strategic space interests by enabling greater participation from diverse commercial actors. Ultimately, ensuring that space contractors are adequately protected from foreign threats is essential to maintaining America’s leadership and operational capacity in space.

KEYWORDS: Space Law, Government Contracts, Indemnification, Risk Mitigation, Commercial Space Industry.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the 1995 film *Apollo 13*, NASA flight director Gene Kranz, played by Ed Harris, makes the infamous proclamation that “Failure is not an option.”² This statement of courage and hope in the face of seemingly insurmountable odds of disaster for the crew of the Apollo 13 crew fittingly represents the laudable efforts of the 20th century American heroes who pioneered human spaceflight. In both the movie and reality, Kranz and the rest of NASA were able to bring the Apollo 13 astronauts home safely, but as it turns out, the legendary line was solely the creation of Hollywood screenwriters. Indeed, there is no evidence that Kranz ever said anything of the sort.³ Perhaps Kranz never would have said such a thing, for he knew very well that failure is very often an option for humanity’s forays into space. The history of space technology all too harshly indicates that failure of some sort is an inevitability.

In the decades since the Apollo missions, the nature of spaceflight has dramatically changed. Particularly since the retirement of the Space Shuttle, partnerships between commercial space operators and the federal government dominate the American aerospace sector.⁴ Contract awards from NASA and the Space Force totaled a record \$29.9 billion in 2023.⁵ This increase from \$26.7 billion in 2022 was due, in part, to increased funding for big-ticket items such as NASA’s Human Landing System and Mars Sample Return Program.⁶ These contracts represent massive line items for the federal budget, and the funding that the contract payments provide to the commercial space industry is essential for its continuing vitality. In the realm of space contracts, where billions of dollars are at stake and failure is an inevitability, methods for mitigating risk are of paramount concern.

This Article begins by describing the various species of risk that space contractors may encounter. After surveying the means of mitigating these risks available in both the marketplace and the procurement process, the Article identifies the potential that foreign adversaries will interfere with and cause losses for space contractors as a crucial type of risk for which there are yet incomplete solutions. Finally, the Article suggests that Congress may address this problem by extending special statutory authority to agencies that contract with space companies.

2. RISK IN SPACE

2.1. *Direct Loss Due to Misadventure*

There are three broad categories of risks that space contractors face. First, there is the ever-present risk that the contractor’s space technology will fail and that this failure will cause significant first-party economic loss, also called direct loss. As space technology becomes more versatile and grows in its applications, the potential for direct loss exposure for these companies increases.

One of the more common forms of government contracts in the aerospace industry is a contract for launch services. In April of 2025, the U.S. Space Force tapped commercial space companies SpaceX, United

² *Apollo 13* (Imagine Entertainment 1995).

³ Associated Press. (2020, April 9). *Apollo 13’s most famous quotes originated in Hollywood*. AP News. <https://apnews.com/article/hollywood-apollo-13s-famous-quotes-7c65759a64b04d0a979e3f4a62c4fced>.

⁴ See NASA, *Commercial Crew Program: Program Essentials*, <https://www.nasa.gov/humans-in-space/commercial-space/commercial-crew-program/commercial-crew-program-essentials/> (last visited Mar. 7, 2026) (explaining how the retirement of the Shuttle led NASA to rely on commercial partners for launch services).

⁵ Siken, J. (2024, January 17). *Record \$765B in federal contracts awarded in 2023*. HigherGov. <https://www.highergov.com/reports/765b>.

⁶ *Id.*

Launch Alliance, and Blue Origin for a new batch of launch services.⁷ These contracts are worth a combined \$13.5 billion through 2029.⁸ Historically, these launches were accomplished with single-use rockets.⁹ Beyond the loss of the payload, the failure of these rockets generally posed no greater risk of economic loss to the operator because the rocket had no ongoing economic utility beyond the single launch for which they were produced. However, several companies have recently begun to operate or plan to soon operate reusable rocket technology.¹⁰ Since rocket reuse promises to be up to 65% cheaper than building a new rocket,¹¹ these launch companies have a strong economic interest in the safe return of the hardware. Where reuse is possible, a launch entails not only a risk of failure for the mission and loss of the payload, but also the risk that the company will lose a significant financial investment in the rocket itself.

Satellite operators, as another example, often stand to suffer significant direct loss when hardware breaks down or is damaged. In 2020, when the number of satellites in orbit was significantly lower than it is today,¹² space debris alone caused losses of an estimated \$79-102 million.¹³ While the financial risk of deploying communication satellites is already well known, space-based data centers, an idea fueled by the recent AI boom, elevate these concerns even higher. These platforms would require large, vulnerable and expensive features such as radiation shielding, radiator panels and computation hardware, further tying up the capital of cutting-edge space companies in vulnerable orbital assets.¹⁴ Similar to the development of reuse technology for orbital rockets, the advancement of satellite technology into the realms of orbital refueling also prolongs the economic utility of some orbital assets. A satellite operator that intends to significantly extend the usefulness of a satellite by periodically refueling will undoubtedly be more sensitive to risks to the satellite, especially those that arise early after its initial deployment.

In the standard launch contract that a commercial satellite operator solicits from a commercial launch company, “[n]either the satellite manufacturer nor the launch services provider accept[s] any liability for satellite or launch failures following intentional ignition.”¹⁵ Instead, parties rely on commercial satellite insurance.¹⁶

2.2. Direct Loss Due to Interference

The second species of risk that space contractors face is the possibility of damage or interference at the hands of adversaries. Though, like the first category, it threatens space companies with direct loss, it is analytically distinct because of the unique challenges it poses to contractors.

⁷ Roulette, J. (2025, April 4). *SpaceX, ULA, Blue Origin clinch \$13.5 billion Pentagon launch contracts*. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/business/aerospace-defense/spacex-ula-expected-clinch-multibillion-dollar-contract-key-pentagon-launch-2025-04-04/>.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ Stockley, A. (2023, April 12). *The rise of reusable rockets: Transforming the economics of space travel*. KDC Resource. <https://www.kdcresource.com/insights-events/the-rise-of-reusable-rockets-transforming-the-economics-of-space-travel/>.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² David Osoro et al., *Emissions Assessment of Low Earth Orbit (LEO) Broadband Megaconstellations*, ADVANCES IN SPACE RESEARCH (forthcoming 2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2025.11.036>.

¹³ Nodir Adilov et al., *An Estimate of Expected Economic Losses from Satellite Collisions with Orbital Debris*, 10 J. SPACE SAFETY ENG'G 66 (2023).

¹⁴ Jeremy Hsu, *Data Centers in Space Aren't as Wild as They Sound*, SCIENTIFIC AM. (Dec. 9, 2025), <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/data-centers-in-space/>.

¹⁵ Segal, R., & Kaufman, S. (n.d.). *Satellite systems procurement: A brief how-to guide*. NASA Space Science and Viability Initiative. https://s3vi.ndc.nasa.gov/ssri-kb/static/resources/05444_Satellite_Procurement_Updated_04BM_7557.pdf.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

Two characteristics of outer space make space assets particularly vulnerable to risk from adversaries. First, the Outer Space Treaty prevents member States from asserting sovereignty over any orbital position or planet, so assets in space are not sheltered by any kind of border or boundary.¹⁷ Instead, they fly in an inherently international regime to which all space-faring states have lawful access. Second, space technology has critical warfare and defense applications. Despite the aspiration of the Outer Space Treaty that space will be used only for “peaceful purposes,”¹⁸ space is increasingly another theatre of international conflict. Indeed, hostility in space is no longer just a matter of science fiction. In the war in Ukraine, Russia has already demonstrated the capability to jam satellite communication networks.¹⁹ Notably, Russia developed technology specifically for the purpose of interfering with the Starlink satellite constellation, a private system owned and operated by SpaceX, an important contractor for the US government.²⁰

Several nations (including the US, China, India, and Russia) have tested Direct-assent ASAT (anti-satellite) missile technology that can completely and permanently destroy orbital assets, rendering them into clouds of dangerous debris that can pose risks to other activities in space for years.²¹ Russia, China and the United States (both the Department of Defense and private companies within the US) have also developed and demonstrated “RPO” (Rendezvous and Proximity Operations) in which one satellite approaches another in space.²² Some of these satellites have mechanical arms that could be used for grasping or disabling an adversary’s space asset.²³ Moreover, as the scope and complexity of space technology grow, nations will continue to develop new counter-space capabilities that have the potential to interfere with the operations of commercial space operators.

The Trump administration’s plan to construct a “golden dome” in space provides a critical example of the emergence of this problem. President Trump has directed the Department of Defense to explore options for an anti-missile system with a significant space-based component.²⁴ As many as 180 companies have expressed an interest in contributing to the project.²⁵ Many of the companies are smaller startups, including Epirus, Ursa Major and Armada.²⁶ The most public of these proposals comes from a collaboration between SpaceX, Palantir, and Anduril, and it proposes a system composed of hundreds of

¹⁷ United Nations. (1967, January 27). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies* (OST). 18 U.S.T. 2410; 610 U.N.T.S. 205.

¹⁸ *Id.* at Art. I.

¹⁹ Secure World Foundation. (2025). *Global counterspace capabilities 02-28*. https://swfound.org/media/208089/swf_global_counterspace_capabilities_2025.pdf

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ Roman, N. (2024, January 30). *Global status of anti-satellite (ASAT) weaponry and testing*. Alliance for Citizen Engagement.

<https://ace-usa.org/blog/research/research-foreignpolicy/global-status-of-anti-satellite-asat-weaponry-and-testing/>.

²² Weeden, B. (2019, April 12). *The evolution of space rendezvous and proximity operations and implications for space security* [Presentation at the United Nations Disarmament Conference]. United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. https://unidir.org/files/2019-12/Brian%20WEEDEN%20-%20UNDC_RPO_Apr2019.pdf.

²³ *Ibid.*

²⁴ Kube, C., & Lee, C. E. (2025, April 17). *Pentagon working to make Trump’s vision of a U.S. Iron Dome a reality*. NBC News. <https://www.nbcnews.com/politics/national-security/pentagon-working-make-trumps-vision-us-iron-dome-reality-rcna201105>.

²⁵ Stone, M., & Taylor, M. (2025, April 17). *Exclusive: Musk’s SpaceX is frontrunner to build Trump’s Golden Dome missile shield*. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/business/aerospace-defense/musks-spacex-is-frontrunner-build-trumps-golden-dome-missile-shield-2025-04-17/>.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

satellites that both sense and attack enemy missiles.²⁷ Interestingly, the companies have also proposed organizing the system as a “subscription service”: for a periodic fee, the Department of Defense could utilize the network while the private companies retain ownership of the hardware.²⁸

Though the international law governing attacks against privately owned satellites furnishing services to military entities is still in development,²⁹ it is undeniable that a satellite which enables an anti-missile system would be a very attractive target for a foreign hostile.³⁰ Even if the plans for a “golden dome” are never realized, military communication services are increasingly utilizing commercial satellites. Commercial satellites “carry between 80-90 percent of all U.S. military communications, making the U.S. military the global satellite communication industry’s biggest single customer.”³¹ Nor is this trend likely to abate, for it is part of the current U.S. national space policy for the government to “[p]urchase and use United States commercial space capabilities and services, to the maximum practical extent under existing law, when such capabilities and services meet United States Government requirements.”³² This policy includes “hosting Government capabilities on commercial spacecraft ... leveraging satellite servicing or on-orbit manufacturing, and public-private partnerships.”³³

Under the historical procurement model, contractors who sold a satellite bus or rocket to the government were insulated from concerns about getting caught up in international conflict. But now, nearly every satellite in orbit today is “dual use,” meaning that it can perform both military and civilian functions.³⁴ A foreign adversary targeting such a satellite would find it difficult or impossible to target just the military systems without also interfering with its commercial uses. Space contractors that retain ownership and operational responsibility for the space assets involved in government contracts are directly exposed to risk of damage at the hands of those who wish to interfere with the military services that they facilitate.

Some of the large, well-funded contractors may be able to stomach this risk for the chance to capitalize the contract prize, but there are other potential providers that could not place an expensive satellite in space without greater assurance that their investment would be protected.³⁵ Since it is the general policy of the federal acquisition system to provide opportunities for smaller firms to win contracts³⁶ and since doing so ensures a field of competitive and thus cost-efficient contracting options, it is crucial that even smaller space providers have access to sufficient methods of risk-mitigation.

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ See Bourbonnière, M. (2004). Law of armed conflict (LOAC) and the neutralisation of satellites or *ius in bello satellitis*. *Journal of Conflict & Security Law*, 9(1), 43–69. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcsl/kri002>.

³⁰ Mountin, S. M. (2014). The legality and implications of intentional interference with commercial communications satellite signals. *International Law Studies*, 90, 101–197. <https://digital-commons.usnwc.edu/ils/vol90/iss1/12/>.

³¹ *Ibid.* at 114.

³² The White House. (2020, December 9). *National space policy of the United States of America* (p. 20). <https://trumpwhitehouse.archives.gov/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/National-Space-Policy.pdf>.

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ Mountin, *supra* note 35.

³⁵ Kisiel, E. C. (2024, August 21). Indemnification for commercial space services vendors. *Public Contract Law Journal*, 53(3). https://www.americanbar.org/groups/public_contract_law/resources/journal/2024-spring/indemnification-commercial-space-services-vendors/.

³⁶ FAR 19.201(a) (2025) (“It is the policy of the Government to provide maximum practicable opportunities in its acquisitions to small business, veteran-owned small business, service-disabled veteran-owned small business, HUBZone small business, small disadvantaged business, and women-owned small business concerns. Such concerns must also have the maximum practicable opportunity to participate as subcontractors in the contracts awarded by any executive agency, consistent with efficient contract performance ...”).

2.3. *Third-Party Liability*

The final category of risk is the risk of incurring third-party liability. Given the extreme technical precision required to place anything in space, the high rate of failure of space technology comes as no surprise. Of the 4325 space missions that took place between 1957 and mid-way through August of 2020, “339 (7.84%) have failed completely, 102 (2.36%) have failed partially, and 4 (0.09%) have failed before the launch.”³⁷ These rates significantly outpace the rate of accidents for aircraft.³⁸

Since the nature of orbits makes it such that anything in space necessarily traces a worldwide path, the impacts of these failures are far-flung. With orbital paths that cross overhead of population centers and rocket bodies that are large enough to survive re-entry, there is a near ever-present danger around the world that an orbital launch could cause significant harm on the ground.³⁹

Even before space technology reaches the launch pad, it can still pose a risk to humans. Hypergolic fuel, a type of rocket fuel used in a wide range of space operations in the past and the present, is favored for being an efficient and low-cost means of rocket propulsion, but it is highly toxic, corrosive and unstable.⁴⁰ An accident involving these substances would have “a massive environmental impact on all life in the surrounding area” and would also “require extensive & hazardous cleanup operations.”⁴¹ Orbital rockets use a wide range of fuels, not all of which are as volatile as hypergolics, but the combustive nature of all chemical propulsion inherently creates the risk of damage.

Space technology also frequently fails while in flight, often in spectacular and deadly fashion. The history of orbital rockets is littered with debris from explosive accidents. Some of the more notable instances include the Space Shuttle Challenger in 1986, the Ariane 5 in 1996, the Delta II in 1997, the Antares in 2014 and the SpaceX Falcon 9 in 2016.⁴² More recently, in March of 2025, an experimental rocket flown by SpaceX exploded over the Gulf of Mexico, flinging metallic debris over a wide swath of ocean near the Bahamas and the Florida coast.⁴³ Falling space debris can generate significant liability for a space operator. When a USSR nuclear satellite re-entered the atmosphere above Canada in 1978, the debris affected a total area of 124,000 square kilometers.⁴⁴ For claims arising out of the damage caused by the wreckage and by the radioactive contamination, the USSR agreed to pay a multi-million dollar settlement.⁴⁵

³⁷ Nikolaos Sapountzoglou et al., *A Bibliometric Analysis of Risk Management Methods in the Space Sector*, 10 J. SPACE SAFETY ENG’G 13 (2023). It is worth noting, however, that the last six years have seen a remarkable increase in rocket success in orbital launch rockets, especially from SpaceX. If data from these years were included in these numbers, it would undoubtedly change these numbers significantly. Yet this study still goes to show the difficult odds that have faced space companies for the majority of the history of spaceflight.

³⁸ Int’l Air Transp. Ass’n, *2023 Safety Performance Summary* (Feb. 28, 2024) (finding an accident rate of “(one accident for every 1.26 million flights” among all flights worldwide for the year 2023).

<https://www.iata.org/en/pressroom/2024-releases/2024-02-28-01/>.

³⁹ See Michael Byers et al., *Unnecessary Risks Created by Uncontrolled Rocket Reentries*, 6 NATURE ASTRONOMY 1093 (2022) (describing the problem posed by the uncontrolled re-entry of large, discarded rocket bodies).

⁴⁰ Wessels, W. (2023, January). *Hypergolic rocket fuel – A double-edged sword*. Headed for Space. <https://headedforspace.com/using-hypergolic-rocket-fuel/>.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

⁴² Wessels, W. (2025, April 7). *Why orbital rockets sometimes explode before or during launch*. Headed for Space. <https://headedforspace.com/why-rockets-explode/>.

⁴³ Wall, M. (2025, March 7). *Watch fiery SpaceX Starship Flight 8 debris rain down over the Bahamas (video)*. Space.com.

<https://www.space.com/space-exploration/launches-spacecraft/watch-fiery-spacex-starship-flight-8-debris-rain-down-over-the-bahamas-video>.

⁴⁴ M. Pietkiewicz, *The “Liability Convention” in a Clash with Practice – Example of the “Kosmos 954” Satellite*, 97 STUDIA IURIDICA 53 (2023).

⁴⁵ *Ibid.* at 64.

As space technology continues to grow in prevalence and applications, the likelihood that third parties will be affected will undoubtedly grow as well. Plainly, the increasing rate of orbital launches globally creates a stronger likelihood of casualty on the ground caused by falling rocket parts.⁴⁶ There is also the growing risk that collisions with space debris will expose operators to liability if they fail to adequately guard against such hazards.⁴⁷ Though the nascent industry of space mining is not yet so developed as to generate a notable likelihood of third-party liability, it is clear that companies entering this market will face considerable questions about third-party liability on environmental grounds.⁴⁸

In some circumstances, space contractors are legally obligated to carry liability insurance. For example, under the Commercial Space Launch Act, a launch provider or company engaged in re-entry activities must secure a certain amount of insurance or demonstrate financial responsibility by other means.⁴⁹ To the extent that a third-party claim exceeds the amount covered by the requisite amount of insurance, the federal government indemnifies the contractor up to \$1.5 billion (adjusted for inflation).⁵⁰ Congress has also authorized NASA to “provide liability insurance for any user of a space vehicle to compensate all or a portion of claims by third parties for death, bodily injury, or loss of or damage to property resulting from activities carried on in connection with the launch, operations, or recovery of the space vehicle.”⁵¹

3. SOURCES OF INSURANCE AND INDEMNIFICATION

3.1. *The Marketplace*

Privately provided insurance represents an adequate solution to some but not all of these sources of risk. Satellite insurance has seen significant development in its short history. In the early history of spaceflight, satellites were often experimental or military in nature.⁵² This made private insurance impractical, and the risk of loss was retained by the government and space agencies.⁵³ Today, with the falling cost of orbital launches and the prevalence of commercial space companies, private satellite insurers have coalesced into “a relatively small but international community within the insurance industry.”⁵⁴

There are several characteristics of the space insurance industry that prevent space insurance from growing and expanding its coverage capabilities. First, the same complex technological challenges of operating in space that make the enterprise difficult for commercial space firms make it difficult for insurers to characterize and forecast the risks involved.⁵⁵ As the technology becomes more proven, it certainly will be easier to predict risk levels. Nonetheless, it is also certain that space firms will continue to innovate in ways that create novel sources of risk.

⁴⁶ Carmen Pardini & Luciano Anselmo, *On the Need to Assess and Mitigate the Risk from Uncontrolled Re-entries of Artificial Space Objects in View of the Current and Future Developments in Space Activities*, 219 ACTA ASTRONAUTICA 662 (2024) (forecasting an increase in the annual casualty rate from re-entering space hardware to increase to 20% in the near future), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2024.03.057>.

⁴⁷ Hugh G. Lewis, Graham G. Swinerd & Richard J. Newland, *The Space Debris Environment: Future Evolution*, 120 AERONAUTICAL J. 1343 (2016).

⁴⁸ Samson Albert S., *Environmental Protection in Outer Space: Legal Challenges in Regulating Space Debris and Extraterrestrial Mining on the Moon and Mars*, 3 INT’L J. SPACE L. & POL’Y 74, 82 (2025).

⁴⁹ 14 C.F.R. §440 (2025).

⁵⁰ *Ibid.* at §440.19.

⁵¹ 51 U.S. § 20138 (2025).

⁵² Manikowski, P., & Weiss, M. A. (2013). The satellite insurance market and underwriting cycles. *Geneva Risk & Insurance Review*, 38(2), 148–152. <https://doi.org/10.1057/grir.2013.2>.

⁵³ *Ibid.*

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*

Second, the pool of activities through which a space insurer can mitigate potential risk is still small. The number of satellites in orbit has greatly expanded since the time of Sputnik. In July of 2024, it was reported that there were as many as 12,994 operational satellites in orbit.⁵⁶ A significant percentage of these satellites are privately owned (with SpaceX alone operating more than 6,000 in its Starlink constellation and launching more satellites every day).⁵⁷ However, satellite insurance still operates with a much smaller risk pool than insurers in the car insurance market, for example, which might have millions of individual policyholders. Moreover, operators of large constellations (like Starlink), which own a huge fraction of the satellites in orbit, tend to address risk with system redundancy instead of commercial insurance, further reducing the field of customers for satellite insurance. For other kinds of space technology, like lunar landers, the list of operators is very short indeed: only a handful of companies have attempted a soft landing on the lunar surface.⁵⁸

Third, the secretive nature of defense contracts for space platforms or services interferes with the ability to secure insurance from the market. Launch contracts for defense agencies, for example, often involve highly classified payloads.⁵⁹ The launch provider may not be able to disclose the exact nature and function of the payload or even the timing or location of its launch,⁶⁰ making private insurers reticent or unwilling to extend coverage.⁶¹

Commercial solutions are readily available for many types of missions and flavors of liability.⁶² While commercial insurance is struggling, in some instances, to keep up with the innovative, risk-hungry activities of the “New Space” cadre of operators (for example, in the realm of human space flight), private insurance remains the backbone method of protecting most operations in space.⁶³

The standard policy available on the market for satellites is for comprehensive coverage, meaning that it will insure against all kinds of damage except for those which the contract explicitly excludes.⁶⁴ A prominent exclusion in these contracts, however, is one that denies coverage for hostile acts.⁶⁵ These exclusions typically deny coverage for damage caused by sovereigns or their agents in the course of international conflict.⁶⁶ There is yet some uncertainty about how such exclusions in insurance contracts

⁵⁶ Wilson, D. (2024, July 18). *Revealed: Number of operational satellites in orbit, 2024*. CEOWORLD Magazine. <https://ceoworld.biz/2024/07/18/revealed-number-of-operational-satellites-in-orbit-2024/>.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*

⁵⁸ The Planetary Society. (n.d.). *Every mission to the Moon, ever*. <https://www.planetary.org/space-missions/every-moon-mission>.

⁵⁹ Federal Aviation Administration. (2002, April). *Liability risk-sharing regime for U.S. commercial space transportation: Study and analysis*. https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/faaliabilityrisksharing4-02.pdf.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*

⁶¹ *Ibid.*

⁶² See AXA XL, *Space insurance*. <https://axaxl.com/insurance/products/space-insurance>; Marsh, *Aviation & Space: Space and Satellite Insurance*, Marsh (last visited Mar. 7, 2026), <https://www.marsh.com/en/industries/aviation-space/expertise/space.html>; Lloyd's, *Space Risk*, Lloyd's (last visited Mar. 7, 2026), <https://www.lloyds.com/about-lloyds/our-market/what-we-insure/space>.

⁶³ Michał Szwałowski, *Risk and Insurance in the New Space Economy*, in *The Oxford Handbook of the New Space Economy* 439, 447 (2026).

⁶⁴ Kerolle, M., & Capurso, A. (2020). *How to estimate insurance coverage for cybersecurity protection for satellites: A case study*. In *Proceedings of the 71st International Astronautical Congress (IAC) – The CyberSpace Edition* (pp. 1–11).

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶⁶ Shniderman, A. B. (2019). *Prove it! Judging the hostile-or-warlike-action exclusion in cyber-insurance policies*. *Yale Law Journal Forum*, 129, 64–84. <https://www.yalelawjournal.org/forum/prove-it-judging-the-hostile-or-warlike-action-exclusion-in-cyber-insurance-policies>.

might apply to the realm of cyber-conflict.⁶⁷ The prevalence of these exclusions is especially worrisome for space operators due to the growing danger that cyberwarfare poses to space infrastructure. According to the Space Development Agency, cyberattacks already represent a greater danger to satellites than missile strikes.⁶⁸ Since the space insurance market is yet small and uniform in its hesitance in addressing hostile acts, a contractor must try to secure this extra coverage as a contract rider, which, if available at all, may be prohibitively expensive.

In sum, the insurance marketplace has robust solutions for some space contractors' potential for loss, but not for those caused by a foreign adversary. Thus, even if the contract is priced to include the cost of insurance premium, private insurance may not be sufficient or practical to mitigate the risks that a smaller contractor would face in contributing hardware to a program such as the "golden dome" system.

3.2. *The Federal Procurement Process*

The federal acquisition process also represents an incomplete solution. Issues of insurance and indemnification are often left out of the procurement process altogether.⁶⁹ There are a few statutory mechanisms for securing extra-contractual protection from an agency, but these mechanisms are difficult to leverage. Under the Anti-Deficiency Act, the government is prevented from entering into an agreement that would obligate it to spend more than has been appropriated for a given contract unless Congress has specifically authorized it to do so.⁷⁰ Thus, absent legislative approval, a government contract may not include an open-ended indemnification clause for the benefit of the contractor. In Public Law 85-804 (the "Act"), Congress has created a narrow authorization for exceptions to this appropriations restriction. Under this law:

[T]he President may authorize any department or agency of the Government which exercises functions in connection with the national defense, acting in accordance with regulations prescribed by the President for the protection of the Government, to enter into contracts or into amendments or modifications of contracts heretofore or hereafter made and to make advance payments thereon, without regard to other provisions of law relating to the making, performance, amendment, or modification of contracts, whenever he deems that such action would facilitate the national defense.⁷¹

In accordance with the legislative history of the Act, the government has historically used this authority to indemnify contractors for the third-party liability risks involved in "various missile programs requiring the use of highly volatile fuels."⁷²

While the authority granted to the president is nominally effective "only during a national emergency declared by Congress or the President and for six months after the termination thereof or until such earlier

⁶⁷ See *Merck & Co. v. Ace Am. Ins. Co.*, 293 A.3d 535, 551 (N.J. Super. App. Div. 2023), leave to appeal granted, 254 N.J. 506, 298 A.3d 353 (2023); leave to appeal granted, 254 N.J. 522, 298 A.3d 364 (2023) (deciding that a cyber-attack was not covered by a "hostile acts" exclusion because it "was a non-military cyberattack against an accounting software provider" that was not "linked to a military action or objective").

⁶⁸ Erwin, S. (2021, April 14). DoD space agency: Cyber attacks, not missiles, are the most worrisome threat to satellites. *SpaceNews*. <https://spacenews.com/dod-space-agency-cyber-attacks-not-missiles-are-the-most-worrisome-threat-to-satellites/>.

⁶⁹ Segal, *supra* n. 11 ("The typical satellite contract structure, and how title/risk of loss/insurance/warranty issues are handled, is not contemplated by the typical government procurement process").

⁷⁰ Pub. L. No. 97-258, 96 Stat. 877 (1982).

⁷¹ 48 C.F.R. § 52.250-1 (2024). Outside of Public Law 85-804, the military departments also have Congressional authorization to enter indemnification agreements. 10 U.S.C. 2354 (2025).

⁷² Mullen, K. P. (2002, December). *Extraordinary contractual relief under Public Law 85-804* (Briefing Papers No. 02-13).

time as Congress, by concurrent resolution, may designate,⁷³ this limitation is “meaningless” and has never been a basis for denying relief under the Act.⁷⁴ President Obama notably used authority under the Act for a USAID contract despite the fact that there was not a congressionally declared national emergency because “USAID [was] exercising functions in connection with the national defense in the course of complying with its humanitarian mandate.”⁷⁵ Undoubtedly, there are significant political constraints that underlie a presidential decision to extend seemingly preferential treatment to a specific set of contractors or to a specific industry, but the legal hurdles are apparently quite low.

In Executive Order No. 10789, President Eisenhower delegated authority to exercise power under the Act to certain federal agencies.⁷⁶ The list of agencies, revised in the years since the original executive order, now includes the Department of Defense, Department of the Treasury, Department of the Interior, of Commerce, Department of Health and Department of Agriculture, Department Human Services, Department of Transportation, Department of Energy, General Services Administration, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Tennessee Valley Authority, Government Printing Office, and Federal Emergency Management Agency.⁷⁷

The procedures for indemnifying contractors through the Act are encoded in FAR Part 50. This allows the contracting officer to include an indemnification clause “whenever the approving official determines that the contractor shall be indemnified against unusually hazardous or nuclear risks.”⁷⁸ This clause, exemplified in FAR 52.250-1, indemnifies contractors against:

- (1) Claims (including reasonable expenses of litigation or settlement) by third persons (including employees of the Contractor) for death; personal injury; or loss of, damage to, or loss of use of property;
- (2) Loss of, damage to, or loss of use of Contractor property, excluding loss of profit; and
- (3) Loss of, damage to, or loss of use of Government property, excluding loss of profit.⁷⁹

As enticing as these terms are for a risk-wary space contractor, there are several statutory requirements that limit their application. First, the contract must involve activities that are “unusually hazardous or nuclear.”⁸⁰ While nuclear technology may soon be used in space,⁸¹ most space contractors will continue to only qualify for this kind of indemnification if they can demonstrate that the activity in question fits into the “unusually hazardous” category. The Air Force Identification Guide emphasizes the need for a contractor to distinguish between activities that are merely “hazardous” and those that are “unusually” hazardous.⁸² While “the manufacturing, storing, loading, or burning of jet aircraft fuel is hazardous” because “there is a possibility for explosion resulting in death and property damage,” the use of rocket propellants “is unusually hazardous” because “solid propellants are highly volatile and their explosive

⁷³ 50 U.S.C.A. § 1435 (2025).

⁷⁴ Prince, & Garland. (2022, October 26). *Presentation on P.L. 85-804* (Defense Acquisition University, p. 49). [https://www.dau.edu/sites/default/files/Migrate/EventAttachments/727/2022%2010%2026%20DAU%20P.L.%2085-804%20Presentation%20\(Prince%20%20Garland\).pdf](https://www.dau.edu/sites/default/files/Migrate/EventAttachments/727/2022%2010%2026%20DAU%20P.L.%2085-804%20Presentation%20(Prince%20%20Garland).pdf).

⁷⁵ 79 Fed. Reg. 68,757 (Nov. 18, 2014) (authorizing the exercise of authority under Public Law 85-804).

⁷⁶ Exec. Order No. 10,789, 3 C.F.R. 426 (1954–1958), reprinted in 23 Fed. Reg. 8897 (Nov. 15, 1958).

⁷⁷ Mullen, *supra* n. 61, at 4.

⁷⁸ 48 C.F.R. § 50.104-4 (2024).

⁷⁹ *Id.* at § 52.250-1 (2024).

⁸⁰ *Id.* at § 50.104-4 (2024).

⁸¹ Foust, J. (2025, April 8). *Space nuclear power at a crossroads as industry pushes for steady investment*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/space-nuclear-power-at-a-crossroads-as-industry-pushes-for-steady-investment/>.

⁸² U.S. Air Force. (2018, February 15). *Indemnification guide for unusually hazardous or nuclear risks* (Rev. A, originally issued July 7, 1997, p. 3). On file with the U.S. Department of the Air Force.

potential is several times greater than jet fuel.”⁸³ The FAR provisions regarding indemnification, on the other hand, “offer very few elaborations” and “the language of the regulations . . . is not subject to judicial review in the usual sense, because the grant or denial of a contractual indemnity is not subject to judicial review.”⁸⁴ Thus, a space contractor might not be able to reliably predict how the legal contours of the “unusually hazardous” requirement will apply to their operations.⁸⁵

Perhaps a satellite that is a valuable military target and is easily targeted by foreign adversaries is legally engaged in unusually hazardous activity by virtue of its sheer likelihood of being destroyed. But predicting if and how international conflict will affect a contractor’s space assets is difficult to predict and thus difficult for a contractor to demonstrate to a contracting officer or higher agency leadership when requesting protection under the Act.

Returning to the “golden dome” hypothetical, it is not clear how a satellite engaged in looking for enemy missiles would fit into the framework of P.L. 85-804. Arguably, space operations are inherently “hazardous,” but whether they can be classified as “unusually so” is a difficult question. The legislative history of the Act indicates that Congress was specifically concerned about the exposure of contractors to unrestricted liability.⁸⁶ Moreover, the Act has historically been used in contracts for products or services that entail a higher risk of generating third-party claims.⁸⁷ Even considering the orbital collisions and uncontrolled re-entries, a satellite in orbit is unlikely to subject its operator to the kind of expansive third-party liability that Congress had in mind.⁸⁸ Indeed, a contractor with a valuable orbital asset is likely to be far more motivated by the risk of damage to the satellite itself. But those seeking protection against their own loss will not be able to find much of use in the historical applications of the Act.

Second, there are significant procedural hurdles that beset a request for protection under the Act. The authority to insert this clause may be “exercised only by the Secretary or Administrator of the agency concerned, the Public Printer, or the Chairman of the Board of Directors of the Tennessee Valley Authority.”⁸⁹ The requirement of high-level approval slows down the completion of the contract. For example, the Navy leadership only reviews requests under the Act for nuclear indemnification on an annual basis, significantly constraining the project timeline for some contractors.⁹⁰ Also, the authority conferred by the Act may legally only be used as a last resort when other legal authority for indemnification is not applicable.⁹¹ This requirement further adds to a contractor’s procedural burden.

⁸³ Federal Aviation Administration, *Liability Risk-Sharing Regime for U.S. Commercial Space Transportation: Study and Analysis*, FAA 5-9 (Apr. 2002), https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/faaliabilityrisksharing4-02.pdf.

⁸⁴ Administrative Conference of the U.S. (1988, June 9). *Federal government indemnification of government contractors* (Recommendation 88-2). <https://www.acus.gov/sites/default/files/documents/1988-02%20Federal%20Government%20Indemnification%20of%20Government%20Contractors.pdf>.

⁸⁵ See Kisiel, *supra* n. 40, at 13 (“While there is precedent, absent a regulatory determination that space activities are ultrahazardous, indemnification would likely require statutory implementation to ensure the availability of funding based on the scope of potential indemnification”).

⁸⁶ Tolan, P. E., Jr. (2003). Environmental liability under Public Law 85-804: Keeping the ordinary out of extraordinary contractual relief. *Public Contract Law Journal*, 32, 215–222.

⁸⁷ *Id.* at 227.

⁸⁸ Parks, J. (2024, September 4). *How often do satellites crash back to Earth and are there dangers in their return?* Discover Magazine. <https://www.discovermagazine.com/the-sciences/how-often-do-satellites-crash-back-to-earth-and-are-there-dangers-in-their>.

⁸⁹ 48 C.F.R. § 50.102-1 (2024).

⁹⁰ U.S. Government Accountability Office. (2024, March 7). *Defense contracting: DOD should take actions to improve its use of indemnification authority* (GAO-24-106403). <https://www.gao.gov/assets/d24106403.pdf>.

⁹¹ FAR 50.101- 2(b)(2); *see also* FAR 50.102-3(b)(2).

Third, authority under the Act technically only extends to contracts that “facilitate the national defense.”⁹² However, like the “state of emergency” requirement, this does not often pose a problem. The FAR outlines several circumstances in which a finding of facilitation of the nation defense is “automatic”: when the relief is granted due to the correction of a mistake, an amendment caused by government action, or based on an information agreement.⁹³ Even where an “automatic” finding is not provided by the FAR, it can generally be established merely by showing that a benefit will flow to the government.⁹⁴ When the purpose of the contract, however, is “to demonstrate technologies needed to lower purely commercial risk and lead to a commercial vehicle designed to meet the needs of the commercial marketplace, a national defense link cannot be used.”⁹⁵

In sum, P. L. 85-804 is too riddled with substantive and procedural requirements to be a reliable means of protecting space contractors from damage caused by foreign adversaries. However, it should also be briefly noted that NASA has statutory authority to establish separate risk-sharing schemes. Specifically, Section 305 of the NASA Transition Authorization Act of 2017 (P.L. 115-10) provides NASA discretion to indemnify contractors providing launch services and re-entry services against successful claims by third parties for death, bodily injury, or loss of or damage to property ... These claims may originate from launch services and reentry services carried out under the contract that the contract defines as unusually hazardous or nuclear in nature.⁹⁶

Since this authority is restricted to launch and re-entry operations and since those operations must still be “unusually hazardous or nuclear in nature,” this authorization does not meaningfully expand the availability of indemnification beyond what is already available under the Act.⁹⁷ More importantly, it does not give an agency authority to insure contractors for their own loss, which, as previously demonstrated, is a significant concern.

4. RECOMMENDATION

Of the three species of risk that a space contractor might face (financial loss from misadventure, from interference from foreign adversaries, and from third-party liability), there are robust solutions in the marketplace and in the current procurement process to handle all but one. Because of the unwillingness of commercial insurers to expand coverage to hostile acts and because of the narrow scope and uncertain application of P.L. 85-804, contractors who operate dual-use technology in space are insufficiently protected against first-party losses caused by foreign interference.

To remove this hurdle for space contractors, Congress should consider granting new statutory authority to agencies so that they may offer space contractors expanded indemnification against these potential losses. Edward Kisiel made a similar recommendation, writing in the ABA Public Contract Law Journal:

The federal government should indemnify vendors who suffer losses from adversarial action since a commercial spacecraft’s status as a military contractor asset makes it a target for adversarial action ... Indemnification from the U.S.

⁹² P.L. 85-804, 72 Stat. 972 (1958).

⁹³ Mullen, *supra* n. 61, at 6.

⁹⁴ *Id.*

⁹⁵ Federal Aviation Administration. (2002, April). *Liability risk-sharing regime for U.S. commercial space transportation: Study and analysis* (pp. 5–9). https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/faaliabilityrisksharing4-02.pdf.

⁹⁶ National Aeronautics & Space Administration. (n.d.). *NASA Federal Acquisition Regulation Supplement (NFS) 1850.104-371(a)*. <https://www.hq.nasa.gov/office/procurement/regs/NFS.pdf>.

⁹⁷ See also 50 U.S.C. § 21038 (2025).

Government would reduce financial risk for vendors seeking to do business with the Department of Defense and other space agencies.”⁹⁸

Kisiel argues for expanded indemnification that is “informed by international and domestic space law.”⁹⁹ He suggests that the private market serves as a partial solution, but does not evaluate the limitations of the private market nor the current slate of options for indemnification through the procurement process.¹⁰⁰ Regardless, the insight that “the military’s increasing reliance on commercial industry for satellite communications and imagery services creates added risk that an adversary will disrupt services or damage systems” and that “[c]ommercial providers do not currently have good legal recourse for this contingency” is well-founded.¹⁰¹

It might be argued that the government should not expand indemnification to contractors because it would impede the development of the private insurance realm. This concern could be addressed through the structure of the statutory authorization. It could, for example, take inspiration from the Price-Anderson Act. This Act, which is in part designed to “remove[] the deterrent to private sector participation in nuclear activities presented by the threat of potential liability claims following a large accident,” requires that certain Department of Energy Contractors maintain the maximum amount of insurance that is available through private providers.¹⁰² Currently, the maximum amount is \$500 million per nuclear site.¹⁰³ The federal government then indemnifies any liability beyond this amount.¹⁰⁴ Though the Price-Anderson Act currently only protects nuclear contractors for third-party liability, the model could be re-fashioned for certain first-party loss by space contractors.

Notably, the Act has not stifled the development of the private market for nuclear operator insurance. Rather, because there is a threshold of expense at which the Act does not operate, it has “enabled insurers to provide stable, high-quality coverage for nuclear risks.”¹⁰⁵ Thus, a space contractor indemnification system that only addresses the risk that the private insurance market is yet to reach could facilitate the private insurance market while still protecting important government contractors.

There are several reasons why the federal government is in a better position to bear the risk of certain space activities than private space firms. First, this allocation of risk would better align with the growing body of international space law. Returning to the hypothetical contractor that operates a satellite in a constellation forming part of the “golden dome,” if a foreign adversary damaged such a satellite, the contractor’s legal recourses would be sparse. The feasibility of suing another nation in a United States court is curtailed by domestic laws such as the Foreign Sovereign Immunities Act.¹⁰⁶ The main international legal mechanism for establishing liability for harm suffered in space is the 1972 Space Liability Convention. But under this framework, only countries may bring claims against other nations, even if one of the country’s private entities suffered the harm.¹⁰⁷ Similarly, States are ultimately and

⁹⁸ Kisiel, *supra* n. 40, at 10.

⁹⁹ *Id.*

¹⁰⁰ *Id.* at 26.

¹⁰¹ *Id.* at 15.

¹⁰² American Nuclear Society, *The Price-Anderson Act*, Position Statement No. 54 (June 2024), <https://cdn.ans.org/policy/statements/docs/ps54.pdf>.

¹⁰³ Price-Anderson Act: Nuclear Power Industry Liability Limits and Compensation to the Public After Radioactive Releases (2026), <https://www.congress.gov/crs-product/IF10821>.

¹⁰⁴ *Id.*

¹⁰⁵ *Id.*

¹⁰⁶ 28 U.S. §1604 (2025).

¹⁰⁷ Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects, art. VIII, Jan. 29, 1972, 24 U.S.T. 2389, 961 U.N.T.S. 187.

internationally responsible for their national activities in space.¹⁰⁸ Regardless of the domestic arrangement between a procuring agency and contractor, it is the federal government that will be collecting and dispersing claims based on international interference with space assets. The federal government may also recoup its costs through sanctions or other international remedies.¹⁰⁹ Thus, if the government indemnifies a contractor for losses caused by a foreign party, the federal government may have avenues of recourse that a commercial firm would not be able to utilize.

Second, space contractors are in a poor position to anticipate and avoid the dangers of international conflict. Private satellite companies are understandably less informed than the US government regarding the strategies or intentions of its foreign adversaries. Nor are they often completely apprised of exactly what a U.S. agency is doing with the contractor's hardware.¹¹⁰ In other words, a space operator providing services to the United States may find itself caught in the crossfire for circumstances that it could not have anticipated or addressed through insurance. If the federal government were saddled with this risk from the outset, the government could make more efficient decisions about how to best allocate and protect investments in space infrastructure.

5. CONCLUSION

This analysis has been particularly designed to address problems that government space contractors face at present and will face in the immediate future. It is also clear that the continued development of space technology will magnify many of these problems. For decades, the United States has maintained its intention to explore other planets, with the Moon and Mars being priorities.¹¹¹ But the United States is not the only nation with such ideas: Russia and China individually and collectively plan to make use of other planets.¹¹²

When the United States inevitably calls on the assistance of the commercial space industry through the procurement process to accomplish its objectives in these distant realms, the contractors will again have to worry about the possibility of being harmed by America's competitors. If the United States were to have already implemented an effective framework for indemnifying against this risk, it would encourage contractors to continue their critical contributions to American space priorities. Perhaps someday the private market will offer potent solutions for these problems of risk in space, but until that day, the federal procurement process should ensure that these risks do not prevent commercial space operators from contributing to the activities of the United States in the final frontier.

¹⁰⁸ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, art. VI, Jan. 27, 1967, 18 U.S.T. 2410, 610 U.N.T.S. 205.

¹⁰⁹ Kisiel, *supra* n. 40, at 13.

¹¹⁰ Federal Aviation Administration. (2002, April). *Liability risk-sharing regime for U.S. commercial space transportation: Study and analysis*. https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/faaliabilityrisksharing4-02.pdf.

¹¹¹ See Wall, M. (2025, March 3). *Trump wants the US to land astronauts on Mars soon. Could it happen by 2029?* Space.com. <https://www.space.com/the-universe/mars/trump-wants-the-us-to-land-astronauts-on-mars-soon-could-it-happen-by-2029>.

¹¹² Orf, D. (2024, March 20). *China and Russia are building a nuclear reactor on the Moon—together*. Popular Mechanics. <https://www.popularmechanics.com/space/moon-mars/a60215653/russia-china-moon-nuclear-plant/>.